

THE CONCEPT OF PROFESSIONAL THINKING AND ITS PEDAGOGICAL ESSENCE.

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ABSTRACT

This article is aimed at analyzing the essence of the professional thinking of future specialists and teachers from the point of view of the psychological and pedagogical factor, as well as identifying essential mental qualities that characterize the way a person thinks through its stable manifestation in solving various problems. There are synthetic, idealistic, pragmatic, analytical, realistic styles of thinking.

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Introduction

Thinking is the highest form of human intellectual activity, the process of reflecting objective reality in consciousness, and since ancient times it has been constantly studied as one of the main objects of scientific interests of philosophical, pedagogical, psychological and physiological sciences. research.

The ancient philosophers Aristotle, Democritus, Socrates, Epicurus recognized thinking as a unity of the psyche and impressions and were the first to classify the laws and forms of thinking. Philosophers of the new era Dj. Locke, F. Bacon, K. Galvesiy, D. Gumlar defined the manifestation of thinking as: feeling, perception, imagination and reflection.

In classical German philosophy (E. Kant, I. Fichte, F. Schelling, G. Hegel), thinking acts as a symbol of the independence of the subject. German philosophers of the 18th century paid attention to the manifestation of thinking as specific forms arising as a result of labor activity and social practice.

Representatives of the Würzburg school (A. Külpe, A. Mayer, N. Ah, K. Buhler, K. Taylor) tried to conduct an experimental study of thinking in the history of psychology. Contrary to the associative theory, they showed the features of an ordered direction of thinking, showed the decisive importance of thinking in the manifestation of a person's personality through the process of thinking.

Also, representatives of behaviorism, Gestalt psychology and psychoanalysis (B.Skinner, A.Bandura, Z.Freud, A.K.Jung), based on their teachings, investigated the manifestations of thinking as a separate phenomenon and substantiated their views.

Thinking is a tool for understanding the environment, social phenomena, reality, as well as the main condition for human activity. This is the highest cognitive process, reflecting reality more fully and clearly than intuition, perception and imagination.

Thinking is a special function of the human brain. Its neurophysiological basis is the interaction of the first and second signaling systems.

In the process of thinking, a person forms thoughts, opinions, ideas, hypotheses, etc., and they are expressed in the human mind in the form of concepts, judgments, and conclusions.

Main part

Through human thinking, it generalizes reality and indirectly (indirectly) understands the most important connections, relationships and features between things and events. Consequently, a person has the ability to foresee the emergence, development and consequences of social phenomena and events on the basis of certain laws, regulations and rules.

Thinking is an object of study in many areas of science (philosophy, logic, sociology, pedagogy, physiology, cybernetics, biology).

In psychology, thinking is divided into several types according to the degree of generalization of reality, the nature of the means of solving problems, the novelty of situations for a person, the level of human activity (visual action, visual image, practical activity). , theoretical, arbitrary, involuntary, abstract, creative, etc.) are studied separately.

Communication and relationships between people in public life, the educational process and production are also manifested through thinking. In the team, such qualities of thinking as a critical view, self-criticism, evaluation, verification, self-analysis, control, self-control, group reasoning are formed.

The perception of a person by a person is also inextricably linked with thinking. Creative works, discoveries, inventions, proposals are products of thinking. Psychology also studies phylogenetic (the period of the emergence of mankind), ontogenetic (throughout a person's life) historical aspects of thinking. Many complex issues of modern science require a deeper study of the logical processes in thinking.

It should be noted that thinking in the direction of philosophical research arises primarily as a socio-historical process that realizes the cognitive abilities of a person.

In the history of Western psychology, the associative, behavioral, gestural and cognitive directions of the study of thinking are recognized as the main conceptual approaches. Representatives of the direction of associative psychology (D. Hartley, J. Priestley, I. Ten, G. Ebbinghaus, W. Wundt) consider thinking as a process that is due to the associative connection of past connections and current sensory experience, from its main functions deny the state of creative synthesis of existing knowledge and cannot go beyond the boundaries of the subjective world and the world of representations as the main and only object of knowledge.

Thinking is an object of study in many areas of science (philosophy, logic, sociology, pedagogy, physiology, cybernetics, biology). In psychology, thinking is divided into several types according to the degree of generalization of reality, the nature of the means of solving

problems, the novelty of situations for a person, the level of human activity (demonstration of actions, demonstration-image, practical, theoretical, arbitrary, involuntary, abstract, creative, etc.). separately. Communication and relationships between people in public life, the educational process and production are also manifested through thinking. In the team, such qualities of thinking as a critical view, self-criticism, evaluation, verification, self-analysis, control, self-control, group reasoning are formed. The perception of a person by a person is also inextricably linked with thinking. Creative works, discoveries, inventions, proposals are products of thinking. Psychology also studies phylogenetic (the period of the emergence of mankind), ontogenetic (throughout a person's life) historical aspects of thinking. Many complex issues of modern science require a deeper study of the logical processes in thinking. Thinking is the activity of the brain, thanks to which a person can represent and express with the help of words and images various states of his body, real and abstract bodies and phenomena of existence. As can be seen from the general classification of thinking, words and images play an important role in this basic function of human brain activity, i.e., through the interaction of direct and verbal influence with various activities of the body, the emerging temporal relationships. In this case, temporal relations are the physiological apparatus of thinking, its analytic-synthetic mechanism. As a result of the analysis and synthesis of stimuli and the activity of the body's reaction to them, temporary connections are not only accumulated in memory, but also extracted from them and serve as material for creating new connections and constantly forming connections from them. does. These mechanisms are characterized by self-management and continuous activity, as a result of which they retrieve temporary connections stored in memory, create new and systematic connections from them, and form from them a complex with constantly formed associations. In modern physiology, these mechanisms are considered reflex, but this does not deny the existence of circulatory processes that underlie self-regulation within the framework of reflexivity.

We have already said that although the laws of the formation of temporal relationships in humans have in common with those in animals, there are qualitative differences between them. Because of this, the thinking of humans and animals is also different from each other. I. P. Pavlov recognized that animals, especially dogs, have the ability to "understand", "put forward hypotheses", "think". According to him, the "thinking" of a dog is the result of the analysis and synthesis of stimuli that affect its senses. A person has a higher thinking, and due to the presence of a second signaling system, this thinking is based on a deviation from reality. Learning (experience), thinking, thinking, meaning is the process of forming temporary connections, and their use is understanding.

Man's way of thinking. An independent person makes a decision as a result of the influence of objective conditions and subjective factors that exist in a humane, democratic society. Although objective conditions are decisive in the formation of an independent personality, subjective factors: the family, preschool institutions, general education schools, secondary specialized and higher educational institutions, labor collectives, microdistricts, political parties, cultural and educational associations and other public organizations are of decisive importance. incomparable impact on educational and ideological work under a single program.

An independent person embodies three main components: independent thinking, independent work and independent living. These components work in close interaction and

undoubtedly influence each other. But the independence of a person depends, first of all, on his ability to think. Thanks to the same ability, a person determines the essence of phenomena, events, processes that he sees, knows, hears happening around him, whether they are right or wrong, true or false. To be more specific, thanks to the same ability, a person finds solutions to the problems that arise in his daily life.

Specific characteristics and levels of manifestation of different types of thinking in solving problems and tasks of a certain content make it possible to comprehend the features of the human mind (depth, breadth, flexibility, critical observation, speed and independence).

Conclusion

A unique combination of mental qualities characterizes the way of thinking of a person through its stable manifestation in solving various problems. There are synthetic, idealistic, pragmatic, analytical, realistic styles of thinking.

Summing up, we can say that thinking in psychology is divided into several types according to the degree of generalization of reality, the nature of the means of solving problems, the novelty of situations for a person, the level of human activity (visual action, visual - figurative, practical, theoretical, arbitrary, involuntary, abstract, creative, etc.).

Thus, the concept of "professional thinking" appears as a form of thinking that determines the level of maturity of a specialist in the process of carrying out a particular professional activity, which does not have a clear definition generally accepted in science.

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